

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF SQUEEZE CAST ZINC-ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The low material and processing costs of zinc-aluminum alloys have increased the employment of the alloys over cast aluminum, bronze, and cast iron in automotive applications. However, the elevated temperature ($>100^{\circ}\text{C}$) properties of zinc-aluminum alloys were found to be unsatisfactory. This has limited the extent of applications of the alloys. One viable approach of improving the elevated temperature properties is by reinforcing zinc-aluminum alloys with alumina fibers to form Al_2O_3 /zinc-aluminum squeeze cast composites.

In the case of a squeeze cast composite, the strength of the composite is governed either by the weakest phase or the weakest interface in the composite. In this paper, factors influencing the tensile strength and fracture behaviour of Al_2O_3 /zinc-aluminum squeeze cast composites at both room and elevated temperatures are discussed. These factors include the interfacial strength of fiber/binder, binder/matrix; as well as the strength of binder and matrix phases in contact with the fibers. The effects of different types of binder on the tensile properties of Al_2O_3 /zinc-aluminum composites are also addressed. Optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy were used to evaluate the characteristics of the fiber/matrix interfaces.

KEYWORDS: Zinc-Aluminum; Preform/Binder; Metal Matrix Composites; Fracture Behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

Zinc-aluminum (Zn-Al) based alloys have found considerable industrial applications since their first discovery. This is primarily due to their excellent castability, fluidity, and good mechanical properties [1,2]. These materials are also known for their high strength/density ratio and can therefore compete satisfactorily with other foundry alloys such as copper, aluminum or cast iron. Despite the attractive room temperature properties of Zn-Al alloys, the elevated temperature mechanical properties were found to be unsatisfactory. Essentially, degradation of tensile strength and creep resistance occurs at temperatures around 100°C . Considering the low melting temperature of the

Zn-Al alloys, a temperature of 100°C corresponds to almost 0.49 T_m of these alloys. With this limitation, the extent of applications of the alloys is restricted to those for low service temperature environments.

An attractive possibility of improving the high temperature properties of Zn-Al alloys up to 150°C is by fiber reinforcement to form composite materials. The potential advantages which can be gained include improvement in modulus of elasticity, creep and wear resistance. Similar work on Zn-Al alloys [3-7] has shown the benefit of fiber reinforcement. However, in most of the reported work on Zn-Al composites, the expected improvement in tensile properties in Zn-27Al alloy reinforced with fibers, especially at elevated temperatures, had not been realized despite an improvement in the modulus of the composites. All of the published data [3,7] on alumina fiber reinforced Zn-Al composites have shown either degradation or moderate increase in tensile strength compared to their unreinforced counterparts. In this work, the reason for the low tensile strength of Zn-27Al alloy at 150°C is mentioned; the possible causes for not achieving the expected strength improvement in the Zn-Al composites at the elevated temperature of 150°C are discussed; and the important factors for fabricating improved Al_2O_3 /zinc-aluminum composites are detailed.

2. MATERIALS & EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

All squeeze cast materials evaluated in this work were fabricated at CANMET/MTL. The chemical composition (wt %) of the type of Zn-Al alloy (Zn-27Al) used in this work, is given as follows:

Al	Cu	Fe	Mg	Si	Zn
27.0%	2.06%	0.065%	0.012%	0.012%	balance

Squeeze cast samples were in the form of discs, with dimensions of 80 mm in diameter and 40 mm in thickness. In addition to the Zn-27Al discs, discs reinforced with alumina fibers were also fabricated by squeeze casting. The reinforced discs were produced using 18 vol % alumina (Saffil) fiber. The Saffil alumina fibers (made by ICI), were reported to consist of 96-97% delta alumina and 3-4% silica. Some of the essential physical and mechanical properties of the Saffil alumina fibers are listed in Table 1.

The squeeze casting of Zn-27Al composites consisted of two stages. The first stage was the preform fabrication, while the second stage was the pressure infiltration of molten metal into the preform. In the preform fabrication stage, the alumina fibers were held together by a binder to form a preform. The function of the binder is to provide a body, consisting of a three dimensional network of inter-connecting fibers. With the present preform processing technique, the fibers are mostly aligned randomly in the transverse plane of the preform. After the preparation of a preform, the preform was placed in a die and preheated to about 400°C. The pressure infiltration stage began by introducing a superheated Zn-27Al alloy (about 80°C above its melting temperature) into the preheated die. A punch was then gradually lowered into the die, forcing the molten metal to infiltrate into the preform. The pressure exerted by the punch on the molten metal was steadily increased to a pre-determined level of approximately 70 MPa (In this work, pressures of 27 MPa and 95 MPa were used). The applied pressure at the pre-determined level was maintained until the molten metal was completely solidified in approximately 1.5 minutes. On completion of the squeeze casting operation, the punch was then retracted from

the die and the composite product was removed from the die by an ejector fitted in the bottom of the die.

In this study, alumina fiber preforms with SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 binders were employed. These preforms were supplied by Zircar Ltd. The surface morphological features of fibers with the SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 binders are shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. From these figures, it is clear that the binder is normally present both at the connecting points between fibers and on the fiber surface. Comparing the two figures, fibers with the SiO_2 binder show smoother surface morphological features than those with Al_2O_3 binder.

The squeeze cast samples prepared for evaluation in this work were as follows: (i) Squeeze cast Zn-27Al, squeeze cast with 95 MPa; (ii) Squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ with SiO_2 binder, squeeze cast with 27 MPa pressure; (iii) Squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ with SiO_2 binder, squeeze cast with 95 MPa pressure; and (iv) Squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ with Al_2O_3 binder, squeeze cast with 95 MPa pressure.

For tensile testing, sub-sized specimens complying with ASTM standard E-8, with 6.35 mm gauge diameter, 25.4 mm gauge length and button ends were machined from the squeeze cast discs. Testing was performed on an Instron model 8562 tensile testing machine using a strain rate of $3.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and an extensometer for recording the strain. Test temperatures were room temperature and 150°C controlled within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy were used to evaluate the characteristics of the fiber/matrix interfaces.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Metallography The Zn-Al alloys are known to have relatively complex multi-phase microstructures. In the case of a Zn-Al alloy containing 27% aluminum (Zn-27Al), solidification of the melt begins with the formation of Al rich dendrites (α phase) and proceeds with the formation of proeutectic β phase around the primary dendrites. The residual liquid solidifies according to the eutectic transformation $L \rightarrow \beta + \eta$. On further cooling, the β phase transforms following the eutectoid reaction ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha + \eta$), thus the resulting Zn-27Al consists mainly of lamellae of $\alpha + \eta$ and of η phases. A copper-rich ϵ phase (CuZn_4), is formed in the Zn enriched interdendritic regions.

The presence of the above phases is shown in a polished section of a Zn-Al sample containing approximately 27% Al, which was observed with back scattered electron mode of a scanning electron microscope to provide an atomic contrast image (Fig. 3). In this figure, the dark regions (1) represent the primary cores of Al rich $\alpha + \eta$ eutectoid which are surrounded by light regions (2) of Zn rich $\alpha + \eta$ eutectoid. The light regions display a continuous rim of fine η precipitate in an α matrix (3), resulting from eutectoid transformation. The white interdendritic regions (4) are Zn rich η phase with islands of $\alpha + \eta$ phase (5) resulting from the transformation of the eutectic β phase.

The incorporation of fibers in the Zn-27Al alloy had a slight modification to the microstructure of the Zn-27Al alloy. In the alumina preform, the Al_2O_3 fibers are

Figure 1. Scanning Electron micrograph of the Al₂O₃ fibers of a preform fabricated with SiO₂ binder.

Figure 2. Scanning Electron micrograph of the Al₂O₃ fibers of a preform fabricated with Al₂O₃ binder.

held together in a three dimensional interconnecting network by a SiO_2 or Al_2O_3 binder. During the squeeze casting operation, the molten Zn-27Al alloy has to infiltrate this network and solidify between the fibers. With the constraint of the fiber spacing, a finer dendrite size in the squeeze cast composite was resulted. Considering that the thermal conductivity of the ceramic fibers is smaller than that of the Zn-27Al alloy and since the preform is preheated prior to squeeze casting, the overall cooling rate was therefore probably lower for the reinforced castings than for the unreinforced alloy. As a result, the extent of dendritic segregation in the reinforced alloys was lower and a more homogeneous microstructure was obtained. Figure 4 shows the microstructure of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite. A closer view of the microstructure shows that the dendrites have grown predominantly into the spaces between fibers, so that the latter are mostly surrounded by zinc rich phases. This observation rules out the possibility of fibers acting as nucleation sites for the Al rich primaries in the matrix alloy. A continuous network of η and η/zinc rich eutectoid interfaces is still apparent in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites.

3.2. Tensile Properties and Fractography The U.T.S. results of the squeeze cast Zn-27Al alloy and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites fabricated in this work are listed in Table 2. Compared with the unreinforced alloy (U.T.S. 156 MPa), the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite fabricated with alumina binder exhibited an U.T.S. of 270 MPa which is a 75% increase in strength. Substantial improvement was also found in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites fabricated with SiO_2 binder. In changing the squeeze casting pressures of 95 MPa to 27 MPa, a decrease in composites U.T.S. from 254 MPa to 240 MPa was obtained. It appears that higher U.T.S. values were measured on specimens fabricated using a higher squeeze casting pressure. Similarly, higher squeeze casting pressure also offers higher ductility composite (Table 2). The test data clearly indicate that at 150°C , the benefits of fiber reinforcement were realized by providing much improved strength.

It has been established that for unreinforced Zn-Al containing approximately 27% Al, when tested at 25°C , the fracture mode is primarily transgranular, although occasionally cracks have been found to propagate through the η phase and along the η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces. However, when the material is tested at 150°C , the fracture path proceeds preferentially along the η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces and through the η phase, resulting in a fully interdendritic failure (figure 5). It is considered that at elevated temperature, the transition from a transgranular to an intergranular mode of failure is the result of the weakening of the η phase and η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces. Such a transition results in a decrease in tensile strength of the alloy. When the Zn-27Al was reinforced with 18 vol% Al_2O_3 fibers, the fracture behaviour was found to be somewhat different when tensile tested at 150°C . In essence, the failure mechanism was not entirely by intergranular mode, rather, a mixed mode of failure was observed. As shown in figures 6a and b, the fracture path proceeded through the η phase, η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces, the $\alpha + \eta$ phase, and the fibers. It is interesting to find that in a region depleted of Al_2O_3 fibers, the failure mode retained those of interdendritic failure along the η phase and η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces (Figure 6a). The increase in the tensile strength of the composite, tends to suggest that the weak η phase and η/zinc -rich eutectoid interfaces which were the preferred fracture path in the case of unreinforced alloy, has been strengthened by the fiber reinforcement.

Figure 3. Atomic contrast micrograph (with Back Scattered Electron mode) of an as polished unreinforced squeeze cast Zn-Al alloy.

Figure 4. Atomic contrast micrograph (with Back Scattered Electron mode) of an as polished squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite.

3.3. Interfacial Characteristics From the mechanical property standpoint, the present finding is quite different from the published data [3,7] which claimed that there was either a decrease or marginal improvement in the elevated temperature tensile strength of Zn-Al alloys (containing approximately 27% Al) when reinforced with Al₂O₃ fibers. The reason for getting low U.T.S. values in those composites [3,6] was attributed to the fact that cracks nucleated and propagated in the brittle binder material and led to premature failure of the composites. Considering that the Al₂O₃ fibers were inter-connected and partially covered by the binder material, the fiber/matrix interfaces actually consisted of a Al₂O₃/binder/Zn-Al layer. It is possible that fracture could propagate either along the binder/Zn-Al or the Al₂O₃/binder interfaces, or through the binder layer. Such a trend was found in an Auger Electron Spectroscopy (AES) investigation of in-situ fracture surfaces of 24 vol% Al₂O₃ reinforced Zn-32Al showing that fracture occurred through the SiO₂ binder layer present at the fiber/matrix interface [6]. AES point analyses and compositional depth profiles demonstrated that SiO₂ was present both on the fiber surfaces and in the depressions left in the matrix by decohered fibers.

In view of the difference in mechanical test data obtained in the previous work [3] and in this work, the interfacial characteristics of a specimen from each case were examined with the transmission electron microscope (TEM). Both specimens were Al₂O₃/Zn-Al containing Zn-Al with approximately 27 % Al, and SiO₂ was the binder material. In the 1st specimen, 24 vol% fiber was used, and the reported U.T.S was 183 MPa [3]. In the 2nd specimen, 18 vol% fiber was used, and the reported U.T.S. was 254 MPa (present work). Figure 7 and 8 show the transmission electron micrographs of the interfacial regions of Al₂O₃/Zn-Al of the 1st and 2nd specimen respectively. In the case of figure 7, a thick SiO₂ binder region of approximately 0.5mm in thickness is present between two fibers. In fact, patches of SiO₂ inter-connecting the fibers were commonly observed and most fibers examined were covered with SiO₂. In addition, cracks in the SiO₂ region were also found. The inter-fiber region of the 2nd composite is shown in figure 8. Quite contrary to the 1st specimen, binder material could hardly be detected in this composite specimen. Thus, the higher strength of the 2nd specimen could be attributed to the lesser amount of fracture prone binder it contained.

Two different types of binder (SiO₂ and Al₂O₃) were used in fabricating composites in this work. In both materials, minimal amount of binder material were detected in the interfacial regions of the composites when examined with TEM. A slight increase in U.T.S. was measured in the specimen prepared with alumina binder (270 MPa) versus the silica binder (254 MPa), when tested at 150°C. In view of the fact that minimal amount of binder material were found in both specimens, there appears to be no other contributing factor which could account for a difference in their mechanical properties.

3.4. Estimation of Composite Strength It is of interest to estimate the expected tensile strength of Zn-Al composites at elevated temperatures and compare with the measured tensile data. Several models [9-12] have been proposed for estimating the strength of composites. In adopting the model proposed by Kelly & Davies [9], and using the Rule of Mixtures (ROM) approach, the basic ROM equation gives,

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

where σ_c and σ_f are the composite and fiber strength respectively. σ_m is the flow stress in the matrix at the fracture strain of the fiber. To account for the discontinuity and randomness of the fibers in the matrix, equation (1) is modified to become,

$$\sigma_c = 3/8 \sigma_f V_f (1 - l_c/2l) + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (2)$$

the value 3/8 takes into the consideration the random orientation [12] of the fibers in the planar direction. The random orientation of fibers in the preform is evident in figure 1. In some cases, a value of 1/5 instead of 3/8 is used if the fibers are considered to be truly random in all directions. The term $(1 - l_c/2l)$ is introduced to account for the critical length (l_c) required for transferring the stress from the matrix to the fibers, and l is the mean length of the fibers. The value l_c , accordingly to Kelly & Davies [9] can be represented by,

$$l_c = \sigma_f d / 2 \tau \quad (3)$$

where d is the diameter of the fiber and τ is the shear strength of the fiber-matrix interface. Very often τ is assumed to be one half the tensile yield strength of the metal matrix. With the data listed in Table 1, along with the measured value of σ_m and the data on the mechanical properties of Zn-27Al alloy in Table 2, equation (2) can be used to estimate the tensile strength of the composites evaluated in this work. Table 3 summaries the measured values of the mechanical properties of Zn-27Al composites, along with the estimated data from the model proposed by Kelly & Davies [9] for comparison. The measured data seem to be comparable with the data estimated by the theoretical model [9].

4. DISCUSSION

From the fracture standpoint, it is understood that when a material fails, the fracture path tends to propagate along the weakest phase or interface in the material. With the introduction of alumina fibers in the Zn-27Al alloy, new interfaces are created. It has been mentioned earlier that the binder film present on the fiber surface of the preform, was retained on the fiber surfaces even after the squeeze casting operation. Considering that the Al_2O_3 fibers are partially covered by the binder material, the fiber/matrix interfaces actually consist of Al_2O_3 /binder/Zn-27Al layers. It is thus expected that fracture could possibly propagate along the binder/Zn-27Al interface, the Al_2O_3 /binder interfaces, through the binder layer, or η phase and η /zinc rich eutectoid interfaces.

Previous study had shown that the tensile strength of Zn-27Al at room temperature was significantly decreased when tested at 150°C. The reason for the degradation in tensile strength of Zn-27Al alloy at elevated temperature is due to the weakening of the interdendritic η phase and η /zinc rich eutectoid interfaces at elevated temperature. The weakening of the above phase and interface has also resulted in a change in failure mode from transgranular mode at room temperature to fully interdendritic mode at elevated temperatures.

In examining the fracture surfaces of Al_2O_3 /Zn-27Al composites tested at 150°C, it was found that there was no tendency for cracks to propagate preferentially along a particular phase or any of the newly created interfaces in the composite.

In essence, failure of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites at 150°C was not by intergranular mode, as in the case of unreinforced alloy, rather, a mixed mode of failure was observed. The fracture path proceeded through the η phase and $\eta/\text{zinc-rich}$ eutectoid interfaces, the $\alpha + \eta$ phase, and the fibers. However, in regions where fibers were depleted, fracture tend to proceed along the η phase and $\eta/\text{zinc-rich}$ eutectoid interfaces as in the case of unreinforced counterpart. Consequently, it is important to achieve uniform distribution of fiber in the matrix, otherwise, failure will initiate in the unreinforced η phase and $\eta/\text{zinc-rich}$ eutectoid interfaces. Since it was found in this work that the tensile strength of the composite was improved to 270 MPa compared to 156 MPa of the unreinforced alloy, this means that the weak η phase and $\eta/\text{zinc-rich}$ eutectoid interfaces, which were the preferred fracture path in the case of unreinforced alloy, had been strengthened by the fiber reinforcement.

The previous Auger work [6] indicated that the possible low tensile strength in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-Al}$ composites could be due to crack nucleation and propagation in the binder material. The TEM work confirmed the presence of a thick layer of SiO_2 binder in the low tensile strength composite but not in the high strength composite. In addition, cracks were found present in the thick SiO_2 region. Therefore, the amount of binder used should be minimized. In this work, two different types of binder, such as SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 were employed for fabricating $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites. In both cases, minimal amount of binder material were detected. And in both cases, no distinct difference on the tensile properties of the composites tested at 150°C was found, and both showed significant improvement in strength when compared with the unreinforced alloy.

The composite tensile strengths obtained in this work are comparable to the composite strengths estimated using the Kelly & Davies [9] model, thus showing the improvement of the elevated temperature strength of Zn-27Al by fiber reinforcement is achievable.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. It is considered that the poor tensile strength of the Zn-Al composites reported earlier can be related to factors such as the presence of a thick layer of brittle SiO_2 binder at the fiber/matrix interfaces; low squeeze casting pressure; and nonuniform distribution of fibers in the matrix.
2. It is possible to strengthen the weak η phase and $\eta/\text{zinc-rich}$ eutectoid interfaces of Zn-27Al at elevated temperature by incorporation of alumina fibers in the matrix.
3. The improvement of elevated temperature (150°C) U.T.S. of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites can be as high as 75% compared to the unreinforced Zn-27Al.

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Figure 5. Atomic contrast micrograph (with Back Scattered Electron mode) of a sectioned and as polished tensile specimen (squeeze cast unreinforced Zn-Al tested at 150°C), showing the $\eta + \epsilon$ interdendritic phases at the fracture surface.

Table 1. Physical and Mechanical Properties of Saffil Alumina Fibers

Length = 1-2 mm	Tensile Strength = 2000 MPa
Median Fiber Diameter = 3 mm	Young's Modulus = 300 GPa
Failure Strain = 0.67%	

Table 2. Mechanical Property and Process Conditions of Squeeze Cast Zn-27Al and Al₂O₃ / Zn-27Al Composites.

Test Sample	Test Temperature (°C)	Yield Strength (MPa)	U.T.S. (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Process Condition
Unreinforced Zn-27Al	150	101±6	156±3	7-13	95 MPa
18 vol% Al ₂ O ₃ reinforced Zn-27Al	150	198±6	240±4	1.0-1.6	SiO ₂ binder, 27 MPa
18 vol% Al ₂ O ₃ reinforced Zn-27Al	150	201±8	254±12	1.6-2.4	SiO ₂ binder, 95 MPa
18 vol% Al ₂ O ₃ reinforced Zn-27Al	150	208±1	270±10	1.1-2.3	Al ₂ O ₃ binder, 95 MPa

Table 3 Estimated and Measured Tensile Strength of Squeeze Cast 18 vol.% Al₂O₃ / Zn-27Al Composites.

	σ_c (MPa) at 25°C	σ_c (MPa) at 150°C
<u>Kelly & Davies [9]</u> $\sigma_c = 3/8 \sigma_f V_f (1 - l_c/2l) + \sigma_m (1 - V_f)$	<u>Estimated Value</u> 433	<u>Estimated Value</u> 232
<u>Experimental Data</u>	<u>Measured Value</u> 439	<u>Measured Value</u> 254

Figure 6a & b. Atomic contrast micrograph (with Back Scattered Electron mode) of a sectioned and as polished tensile specimen (squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite tested at 150°C), showing the $\eta + \epsilon$ interdendritic phases, the fibers and $\alpha + \eta$ phases at the fracture surface.

Figure 7 Transmission electron micrograph of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite, showing the presence of thick region of SiO_2 binder.

Figure 8 Transmission electron micrograph of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite, showing the presence of matrix material in the region between the fibers, and no binder material was detected.

